

Nurse-driven Assessment of Maternal-Infant Attachment in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit

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Background

- Prolonged hospitalization can create stress that will affect the development of healthy mother-infant relationships.
- The NICU setting can negatively impact the infant's future physical and mental health.

Problem Statement

- Currently, the assessment of maternal-infant attachment by nursing staff is not routinely documented.
 - Goal was to increase referrals to psychologist in NICU.
 - Need for nurses to recognize cues of problematic issues in maternal-infant attachment.

Purpose

- Develop and implement an assessment tool for NICU maternal-infant dyads in order to assess mother-infant attachment.
 - Reinforce the importance of early mental health assessment for medically complex infant.
 - Increase referrals to the psychologists in the NICU to support both maternal and infant mental health.

Literature Review

- **Maternal-Infant Attachment**
 - Closeness-The ability for the mother to stay close to her infant by:
 - Breastfeeding
 - Kangaroo care
 - Holding or touching the infant
 - Being actively involved with the decision making and plan of care for her infant Flicking, Thomson, & Axelin (2016)
- **The Neonatal Nurses' Role in the Assessment Maternal-Infant Attachment**
 - Neonatal nurses' interaction with mother.
 - Discharge teaching when appropriate.
 - Engagement in care.
 - Breastfeeding/kangaroo care if applicable.
 - Ability of nurse to promote attachment.
 - Encourage interaction with infant as soon as possible. Flury, Parpinelli, and Makuch (2014)

Theoretical Framework

PDSA model (Deming, 1994, p 132)

Methods

- Design
 - Quality improvement project designed to develop a nurse driven assessment protocol.
 - Create guide for nurses to identify positive and negative indicators of maternal-infant bond.
- Setting
 - 391 bed, Magnet designated children's hospital located in Los Angeles.
 - Level IV NICU unit comprised of 58 critical care beds.
 - Patients are of 1:1 and 1:2 acuity.
- Sample
 - 150 RNs who work in the NICU as bedside nurses.
 - Project was piloted in one zone of the unit with 11 beds.
- Tool Development
 - An expert panel compiled a list of characteristics.
 - Final list was determined, using inter-rater agreement of 90%
- Education of Nurses consisted of:
 - Project purpose and objectives
 - Overview of maternal-infant bonding
 - How to use Nurse Driven Assessment Tool (NDAT)
 - Based on results of assessment tool, request early referral for psychological intervention

Nurse Driven Assessment Tool (NDAT)

Mother Characteristic	Independently	With nurse encouragement	None of the time	Not Applicable/Not observed	Infant reaction (Circle all that apply)
Talking, singing or reading to infant					Calming Makes eye contact Crying inconsolably Turns away Smiles Coo No response
Making eye contact with infant					Calming Makes eye contact Crying inconsolably Turns away Smiles Coo No response
Therapeutic touch such as: Touching infant with gentle pressure or stroking gently					Calming Makes eye contact Crying inconsolably Turns away Smiles Coo No response
Holding and talking to infant					Calming Makes eye contact Crying inconsolably Turns away Smiles Coo No response
Comments					

Results

Participants: 150 RNs: 125 employed by hospital and 25 travel nurses. Day shift: 63 RNs; Night shift: 62 RNs

Results

The nurses responded to the following prompt: Please provide any other comments or concerns regarding the education or use of the tool that may assist in this project.

Nurses responses were:

- "I think the tool is easy to understand and practical to use."
- "I think this is a good tool."
- "Thank you for this education mother/infant bonding is something we don't even highlight because it's so engrained in us as nurses, but in fact this education helps to highlight the fact that the mother/infant bond is important and needs to be assessed more closely."
- "I think it's really great that we're looking at the maternal-infant bond. It would be great to have more education about how the bond affects babies and moms later in life. It would also be great if maybe we had a care plan that we could start of altered maternal bond- we only have a parental one because then we could DARP on it and document more."

- Referrals to Psychologist
 - Prior to project pilot
 - November 2018- 9 referrals 15.9%
 - During project pilot
 - December 2018 – 8 referrals 14.2%
 - Post project pilot
 - January 2019 – 11 referrals 19.5%

Discussion

- Education of the NICU staff nurses accomplished goals
 - Increased awareness of psychology team
 - NICU nurses play important role in promoting closeness of parents
 - Increase ability of parents or mother to readily bond with their infant
- 23 surveys completed
 - Difficult to generalize results based on low response rate
 - Unable to resend survey

Future Considerations

- Education plan will be modified to a more formal process to educate the nurses
 - Psychologists agree to assist with providing education
- NDAT tool to be modified to include fewer characteristics for the infant
 - Seven characteristics listed for infant
 - Four characteristics listed for mother
- Long-term goal
 - Assessment of attachment or infant reactions to maternal interaction will be added to the EMR
 - Development of maternal-infant attachment care plan